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BIM-TECHNOLOGIES IN ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN OF CONSTRUCTION AND CALCULATIONS

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Digital transformation of the built environment industry is a cornerstone. Construction strategy in the world seeks to 'embed and increase the use of digital technology'. Pivotal to this shift is adoption of building information modelling (BIM) which is changing the way design, build, operate and integrate built infrastructure.

This research method consist of surveys, case studies and participant and non-participant observation in coordination of multidisciplinary teams work - Architecture, Structural and MEP specialists. Companies using VDC/BIM technologies optimizes designs, improves collaboration, and expedites the implementation of projects. Make more informed design decisions, automate construction documentation, and produces more constructive designs projects.

Some structural engineering companies begin the design process by creating documentation. Others start by creating an analytical model. The link between VDC/BIM software products supports both of these workflows. However, there are some advantages to starting the design process instead of with creating an analytical model.

By starting the design process, you create both a physical model, for coordination and early documentation, and a simplified analytical model. Each model is independently editable, but also maintains a consistent relationship to the other. Moreover, VDC/BIM software capabilities

enable structural designers to enrich the physical model with information such as physical properties, proposed analytical model definition, and expected loads conditions. This makes the physical model more complete and also enhances collaboration with structural engineers. For example, in a traditional workflow the CAD technician or designer creates a physical model defining expected relations with its analytical representation, which is a simplification of more detailed, real geometry. The CAD technician must then wait until the engineer has completed the structural analysis and design before starting coordination and documentation tasks.

The bidirectional link between VDC/BIM software helps make the exchange of structural analytical information much smoother. The link enables companies to add analysis-related information to the model, use that model (and information) directly for analysis, and then update the model based on the analysis results. This iterative data exchange respects and preserves the information defined in both software solutions.

The international experience of the Architecture & Planning & Designing company UABIM shows that VDC/BIM technologies enables to work more collaboratively - helping to optimize designs, improve accuracy, and connect design and fabrication, produce the one drawing set you can build from.

All these building design advantages allowed company UABIM to win the tender in United Kingdom to services structural analysis and calculation of reinforced concrete structures, produce a shop drawings (working drawings) and design documentation of the frame of the designed building.

Below is a recommended workflow for concurrent structural documentation, design, and analysis:

1. The CAD technician creates a structural model based on an existing architectural model or existing architectural 2D layouts.
2. The structural designer adjusts material and profile definitions, and adjusts the analytical model proposed by BIM software.
3. The designer creates loads and load combinations that can be used for analysis in BIM software. This information can also be used within design and code checking applications.

4. In this fashion, the engineer exploits the interoperability between the software solutions - using analytical model and perform structural analyses.

5. Based on analysis outcomes, the engineer may make decisions that need coordination with the designer (and perhaps ultimately the architect as well). The engineer updates the analytical model with recommended changes and alerts the designer.

6. The designer uses BIM software to review the engineer's recommended changes to the analytical model. In collaboration with the engineer, the designer accepts or rejects the proposed changes to the analytical model and BIM software automatically adjusts the physical model accordingly.

7. This iterative collaboration between the designer and engineer repeats as necessary.

8. The designer may also adjust section sizes and properties, based on information received from BIM software or other codechecking applications.

The findings suggest that the VDC/BIM technologies helps to plan and control construction and as a result increase efficiency, improve quality, cost and risk reduction for construction, improvement of collaboration with stakeholders - Developers, Contractors, Subcontractors.

References:

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